

Photometric determination of zirconium(IV) 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-[2-(5'-methylfuryl)]-4H-chromen-4-one

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Manuscript received 04 June 2009, revised 26 August 2010, accepted 28 October 2010

Abstract : A simple spectrophotometric method for the trace determination of zirconium is developed using 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-[2-(5'-methylfuryl)]-4H-chromen-4-one (CHMFC) as a complexing agent for the metal ion in acid solution. The resulting complex bears a metal to ligand ratio of 1 : 2 whose absorption maximum lies at 430 nm. The method obeys Beer's law in the range 0–1.5 $\mu\text{g Zr}^{\text{IV}} \text{ ml}^{-1}$ with a molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity value of $2.32 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0039 \mu\text{g Zr}^{\text{IV}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ respectively. It is also free from the interference of a large number of cations and anions. Utilizing the proposed procedure, the analysis of various synthetic samples and reverberatory flue dust has been carried out to a greater degree of accuracy.

Keywords : Zirconium, 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-[2-(5'-methylfuryl)]-4H-chromen-4-one, spectrophotometric determination.

Introduction

Recent literature survey reveals that chromones and their derivatives¹⁻⁵ give color reactions with trace amounts of the transition metal ions in acidic medium. This fact can therefore, be investigated further to study the use of such reagents in working out spectrophotometric methods for determination at lower level of various elements. In case of zirconium as well, it is expected that a similar behaviour may be observed in acidic and/or alkaline solution, differing in sensitivity and selectivity of the complex thus formed. In the present case, a chromone derivative, 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-[2-(5'-methylfuryl)]-4H-chromen-4-one (CHMFC) has been exploited with a view to study its complexation behaviour towards the metal ion in order to layout an easy and accurate method for determination of trace amounts of zirconium in aqueous solution.

Experimenta.

Apparatus, reagents and solutions :

A stock solution of zirconium(IV) containing 1 mg Zr/ml is prepared by dissolving a correctly weighed amount of $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in a minimum volume of dilute hydrochloric acid and standardized gravimetrically⁶. Lower concentrations of the metal ion at the $\mu\text{g/ml}$ level are prepared by proportionate dilutions therefrom.

The reagent, 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-[2-(5'-methylfuryl)]-4H-chromen-4-one (m.p. 204–206 °C), was synthesized by the method⁷ as described below in brief, and dissolved in ethanol to give 0.02% solution.

To an ethanolic solution of acrylophenone (2 g in 20 ml) aqueous sodium hydroxide (10 ml, 20%) is added slowly at 0 °C. This is followed by the addition of hydrogen peroxide (8 ml, 30%) dropwise to the resulting dark red slurry with stirring which is continued further for 6 h. The light yellow reaction mixture thus obtained is poured onto crushed ice and neutralised with dil. HCl (1 M). The light yellow solid formed is filtered and washed several times with ethanol to give CHMFC (m.p. 204–206 °C).

Samples :

(i) Synthetic sample solutions are obtained by mixing solutions of Zr^{IV} and other metal ions appropriately.

(ii) *Reverberatory flue dust* : A weighed amount of flue dust from copper manufacture is mixed with a known amount of zirconium and dried in an oven. After fusion of the sample with sodium peroxide (approximately eight times the weight of the sample), the leach is neutralized carefully with conc. H_2SO_4 (18 M) and then made just alkaline. It is boiled and filtered to remove the hydroxide forming elements present in the flue dust and then finally washed several times with distilled water. The filtrate along with the washings is adjusted to contain pH ~7

and zirconium determined as described below in the procedure.

Procedure :

To an aliquot of sample solution containing $\leq 15 \mu\text{g}$ Zr^{IV} in a 100 ml separatory funnel, add 1.0 ml HCl (1 M), 1.0 ml 0.02% CHMFC (in ethanol) and enough deionized water to make the final aqueous volume 10 ml. The contents are gently mixed and the absorbance of the yellow colored species formed is measured at 430 nm against a similarly treated reagent blank. The amount of zirconium is determined from the calibration curve drawn by plotting a graph between varying μg amounts of Zr^{IV} and the corresponding absorbance values obtained, following the above procedure.

Results and discussion

In acid solution, Zr^{IV} reacts with the reagent CHMFC forming a yellow colored species which is quite stable. The complex has hardly any extraction into various organic solvents and hence absorbance measurements are effected in aqueous solution.

Choice of medium :

Keeping aqueous conditions the same (at 1 N for all the acids), the absorbance of the complex is measured, which shows a decreasing trend in HCl, HClO_4 , CH_3COOH , H_2SO_4 and H_3PO_4 , respectively. Similar behaviour is observed in case of NaHCO_3 and NaOH with lower absorbance values. Hence hydrochloric acid provides the suitable medium for working on the system.

Absorption spectrum :

The absorption spectrum of the complex indicates that the maximum lies in the range 428–432 nm, where the reagent blank has relatively much low absorbance value.

Effect of HCl and CHMFC :

The effect of HCl and the reagent CHMFC on the formation and absorbance of the complex is shown in Table 1.

In absence of HCl (without taking into consideration the acid present in zirconium solution), the absorbance is 0.075 which increases to 0.115 when 0.2 ml of HCl (1 M) is present and goes upto a maximum value of 0.254 for 0.8–1.2 ml, indicating a downward trend thereafter. The absorbance falls down to 0.214 for 2.0 ml of the acid.

Without reagent, the absorbance is nil and rises to 0.203 for 0.5 ml of CHMFC (0.02% in ethanol). It increases further to a maximum value of 0.254 for 0.9–1.2 ml of the reagent.

Hence, to achieve maximum absorbance, for 15 μg Zr, 1 ml HCl (1 M) and 1 ml CHMFC (0.02% in ethanol) in 10 ml aqueous solution are the optimum conditions with maximum absorbance at 430 nm.

Beer's law and Sandell's sensitivity :

Beer's law holds good in the concentration range 0–1.5 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of zirconium. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex are $2.32 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0039 \mu\text{g Zr}^{\text{IV}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, respectively at 430 nm. The limit of detection (LOD) of the method is 0.01 ppm. However, the optimum concentration range that can be measured, as evaluated from Ringbom's plot, is 0.5–1.5 $\mu\text{g Zr/ml}$.

Stoichiometry of the complex :

The ratio of Zr^{IV} to CHMFC in the aqueous species has been found to be 1 : 2 by Job's method of continuous variations using equimolar solutions of both ($2.886 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$) and also the same is ascertained by the mole ratio method.

Effect of diverse ions :

The effect of various anions, cations and complexing agents on the absorbance of Zr^{IV} -CHMFC complex is studied under optimum conditions of the procedure using

Table 1. Effect of HCl and CHMFC on the absorbance of Zr^{IV} complex

HCl (1 M) ^a (ml)	0.0	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8–1.2	1.4	1.6	2.0
Absorbance	0.075	0.115	0.161	0.209	0.254	0.243	0.236	0.214
CHMFC ^b (ml)	0.0	0.5	0.8	0.9–1.2	1.5	2.0		
[0.02% (m/v) in alcohol]								
Absorbance	0.000	0.203	0.249	0.254	0.233	0.218		

^a Zr^{IV} 10 μg ; CHMFC (0.02%), 1 ml; aqueous volume = 10 ml; λ_{max} = 430 nm; HCl, variable.

^bHCl (1 M), 1 ml; other conditions are the same as in (a) excepting variation in CHMFC.

Note

10 µg Zr^{IV} in 10 ml aqueous volume. Their tolerance limits are : ascorbic acid, 500 mg; sulphate, bromide, nitrate, 100 mg each; thiourea, sulfosalicylic acid, thiocyanate, chloride, iodide, 75 mg each; acetate, sulphite, 50 mg each; citrate 2 mg; tartrate, 1 mg; H₂O₂ (1% m/v), 1.0 ml. EDTA, phosphate and oxalate, decrease absorbance of the complex.

Amongst the cations, Be^{II}, Ca^{II}, Mg^{II}, Cd^{II}, La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Sr^{II}, Mn^{II}, Sm^{III}, Gd^{III}, Yb^{III}, Nd^{III}, Eu^{III}, Ho^{III}, Dy^{III}, Se^{IV}, Hg^{II}, Hg^I, Au^{III}, Zn^{II}, Pb^{II}, 10 mg each; Ni^{II}, Tl^I, 5 mg each; Co^{III}, 2 mg; Ba^{II}, Re^{VII}, Sb^{III}, 1 mg each; Al^{III}, U^{VI}, Pt^{IV}, 0.5 mg each; As^{III}, 0.2 mg; Rh^{III}, Bi^{III}, Ag^I, V^V, 0.1 mg each; Th^{IV} 0.05 mg are without effect. Hf^{IV} increase the absorbance of the complex.

Table 2. Analysis of synthetic mixtures and real samples by the proposed method

Sl. no.	Sample composition ^a	Zr ^{IV} added (µg) ^b	Zr ^{IV} found (µg) ^b	Standard deviation 'S'	Relative standard deviation 'RSD'
1.	Sr ^{II} (5), Mn ^{II} (5)	5.0	5.00	0.039	0.790
2.	Sr ^{II} (2), Mg ^{II} (5), Mn ^{II} (5)	8.0	7.87	0.079	1.000
3.	Re ^{VII} (1), Zn ^{II} (1), Au ^{III} (5)	5.5	5.54	0.023	0.411
4.	La ^{III} (1), Cd ^{II} (5), Hg ^{II} (5)	4.0	4.13	0.039	0.951
5.	Cd ^{II} (1), Mg ^{II} (2), Re ^{VII} (1)	7.0	7.10	0.060	0.847
6.	Sr ^{II} (1), Sm ^{III} (1), Hg ^{II} (1)	7.0	7.06	0.059	0.848
7.	Zn ^{II} (2), Mn ^{II} (2), Be ^{II} (2)	7.5	7.81	0.059	0.767
8.	Al ^{III} (1), Ca ^{II} (2), Pb ^{II} (0.1)	6.5	6.55	0.023	0.347
9.	Tap water	6.0	6.01	0.023	0.378
10.	Tap water	4.0	4.00	0.023	0.567
11.	Reverberatory flue dust, 100 mg	5.0	4.84	0.079	1.625
12.	Reverberatory flue dust, 100 mg	8.5	8.28	0.060	0.728

^aFigure in parentheses indicates the amount of the metal ion in mg.

^bAverage of triplicate analysis.

Table 3. Comparison of the proposed method of determination of zirconium(IV) with some of the existing methods

Sl. no.	Aqueous conditions	(i) λ _{max} (nm) (ii) Beer's law range (µg/ml)	Molar absorptivity (L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Interfering metal ions	Refs.
1.	Zr ^{IV} , pH 1.4, 3-nitroalizarin	(i) 500 (ii) -	6.25 × 10 ³	Mg ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Nb ^V , Mo ^{VI}	8
2.	Zr ^{IV} , HCl (0.2 M), DBM arsenazo	(i) 520 (ii) -	1.85 × 10 ³	?	9
3.	Zr ^{IV} , pH 2.4-2.6, 4-2-(pyridylazo)resorcinol	(i) 540 (ii) -	7.0 × 10 ³	Co ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Ce ^{IV} , U ^{VI} , Bi ^{III}	10
4.	Zr ^{IV} , pH 0.2-0.8, phenylthiazolyl azo chromotropic acid	(i) 545 (ii) 0.0-1.4	2.2 × 10 ⁴	V ^V , Nb ^V , Ta ^V , Ti ^{IV} , Fe ^{III,II} , Th ^{IV} , Be ^{II} , Mn ^{II} , Hf ^{IV}	11
5.	Zr ^{IV} , pH 4.5-5.5, solochrome azurin BS	(i) 545 (ii) 1.0-4.4	1.09 × 10 ⁴	Mo ^{VI} , U ^{VI} , Th ^{IV} , V ^{IV} , Ce ^{IV} , Fe ^{III} , Bi ^{III} , Al ^{III} , Cr ^{III} , Cu ^{II}	12
6.	Zr ^{IV} , HCl (0.1 M), 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-([2-(5'-methylfuryl)]-4H-chromen-4-one (proposed method)	(i) 430 (ii) 0.0-1.5	2.32 × 10 ⁴	(37 metal ions are non-interfering)	

Conclusion :

The wide applicability of the method is tested by the analysis of several synthetic samples and reverberatory flue dust and the results obtained are highly reproducible as indicated from their standard deviation 'S' and relative standard deviation 'RSD' values (Table 2). The proposed spectrophotometric method is simple, rapid, sensitive and free from the interference of a large number of metal ions and anions. The method compares favourably well with the existing methods⁸⁻¹² particularly in respect of molar absorptivity and interferences (Table 3).

Acknowledgement

Our sincere thanks are due to Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra for providing laboratory facilities and to UGC, New Delhi for the award of Project Associateship to A. Jain.

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